

ELIXIR Data and Interoperability Platforms 2022 Face-to-Face Event Summary Report

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Background

ELIXIR, the European research infrastructure for life science data, has five different Platforms focussed on life science technical activities - these are Tools, Training, Compute, Data, and Interoperability. The ELIXIR Data and Interoperability Platforms held their second joint Face-to-Face meeting last year on the 28th - 30th November 2022. The Face-to-Face meeting was kindly hosted by the ELIXIR Switzerland Node and the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB) in collaboration with the ELIXIR Hub at Campus de Battelle in Geneva, Switzerland. This annual meeting brought together members of the two Platforms in order to work on Platform projects known as Tasks and to facilitate strategic Platform planning for the coming year. A large focus of this year's event was dedicated to discussing and planning the Platform strategies in relation to the forming ELIXIR Scientific Programme for 2024-2028.

Event format and content

The event was hosted over a period of three days through a blended hybrid attendance of 48 in-person and 36 remote attendees.

The first day of the event was opened by the ELIXIR Switzerland Head of Node, Christophe Dessimoz, with an overview of SIB. The Data Platform then focussed on their Tasks with community engagement from the forming ELIXIR Data Management Community representatives and the ELIXIR Biocuration Focus Group and subsequent highlight presentations on scalable curation. The day ended with ELIXIR 2024-2028 Scientific Programme planning and member input.

The second day hosted both Platforms to facilitate both Data and Interoperability topics of overlapping interest. Time was predominantly spent discussing the ELIXIR key service collections run by these Platforms - the Core Data Resources (CDRs) and the Recommended Interoperability Resources (RIRs), as well as the relationships between the two. The CDR session hosted a highlight presentation from the Global Biodata Coalition, and the Interoperability section of the day finished up with presentations from a number of key players in the research data management portfolio.

The final day of the event focused on Interoperability activities, with an emphasis on strategic planning and brainstorming for the upcoming ELIXIR Programme from 2024 - 2028.

A highlight of the joint Face-to-Face was the engaging discussion and interaction that took place between both in-person and online participants, creating a more enriching experience for all attendees.

Significant event outcomes

- Strengthened Platform relations with SIB and Swiss Node members.
- Reinforced connections between Data & Interoperability Platforms.
- Platform member input for the 2024-2028 ELIXIR Scientific Programme Platform planning.
- Improved links of both Platforms with the forming ELIXIR Data Management Community.
- Improved relations between the Data Platform and the ELIXIR Biocuration Focus Group.

Date: 30/01/2023

- ELIXIR Core Data Resources (CDR) status update and planning for 2023 CDR processes established.
- Strengthened relations with the Global Biodata Coalition and the ELIXIR Data Platform.
- Agreement that the scope and purpose of the Recommended Interoperability Resources will be reviewed in 2023 to increase their value for the 2024-2028 Programme.
- Connections between the FAIR Services ecosystem resources and people were strengthened.
- Successful ELIXIR Hub guidelines were established and implemented to facilitate a balanced hybrid experience.

Participant feedback on the event

Post-event survey responses were positive. A point of particular note is that participants enjoyed the hybrid format and the majority of respondents would choose this as their preferred F2F event medium for the meeting in the future. Participants enjoyed the opportunity to interact across ELIXIR Platforms and suggested exploring different Platform combinations to fully leverage the strengths of the different Platforms in 2023.

Conclusion

The event offered a great opportunity for cross-Platform collaboration and strengthening Data and Interoperability Platform relations both internally and amongst several other groups in ELIXIR. The Platforms progressed on their Tasks and successfully laid the groundwork for their respective ELIXIR 2024-2028 strategic plans.